

Effect of plyometric training on muscular power and anaerobic ability of the noviced sprinters

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to examine the effect of plyometric training on muscular power and anaerobic ability of noviced sprinters. The subjects for the present study were selected on the basis of random group design. To test the muscular power and anaerobic ability considered standing broad jump and 50 meters dash. Forty subjects underwent training for twelve weeks with the plyometric training. The difference in the mean of each group for selected variable was tested for the significance of difference by "t" test. The level of significance was set at 0.05. Results shows that the plyometric training have a significant improvement on muscular power and anaerobic ability of the noviced sprinters

Keywords: Plyometric, Standing Broad Jump, 50 meter dash, Noviced sprinters.

INTRODUCTION

Plyometric is a method of developing explosive power. Previously referred to as jumping training the term plyometric first appeared in literature in the late 1960. Yuri verkhoshensky the father of plyometric. Plyometric as a term was formed from the Greek root pleythein which loosely translated means to increase. An American coach by the name of Fred Wilt is believed to be the first person to use the term Plyometrics to describe the jump training that some U.S coaches were implementing with their athletes. The movements traditionally employed in a plyometric training program will involve a pre-stretch and stretch-shortening cycle. Over time, a plyometric training program with result in increased force production due to mechanical factors such as increased stored elastic energy and neurophysiologic factors such as changes in the muscle's force/velocity characteristics. The true purpose of plyometric training is to decrease the ground contact time of an athlete while sprinting, jumping, and throwing. Ground contact time can simply be seen as the phase of time that elapses while the eccentric contraction (stretch) of a muscle group is reversed and the concentric contraction contract of that group begins. Before ever starting a plyometric program, you must assess your previous training experience, age, physical maturity and conditioning, flexibility and strength.

Sample:

The present study had been undertaken to compare the effect of plyometric training on muscular power and anaerobic ability of noviced sprinters. A total of 40 participants of 18 to 25 years in age participated in the current study is selected from district sports stadium, Shahjanpur, U.P. They were divided in to two groups. Group A worked as experimental and Group B as control. Muscular power and anaerobic ability were taken as criterion measures for the study. The data were collected twice on each selected variables i.e., once before the training programme and secondly at the end of twelve weeks training programme.

PROCEDURE

1. Muscular power :Standing Broad Jump.
2. Anaerobic ability : 50 Meters

RELIABILITY OF DATA

The reliability of test score was established by test retest method. The reliability of data is presented in table-1.

TABLE-1

Sr. No.	Test Item	Coefficient of correlation
1.	Muscular power	.88
2.	Anaerobic ability	.83

SIX WEEK OF PLYOMETRIC TRAINING PROGRAMME

The students went through plyometric exercises (for twelve week) through training programme under strict supervision of the researcher. Experimental group practiced following exercise during the training:

1. Single leg speed hop
2. Alternate leg bounding
3. Double leg hop progression
4. Depth Jump
5. Fast skipping
6. Medicine ball chest pass.

RESULTS: The study was conducted to determine the effects of plyometric on muscular power and anaerobic ability of noviced sprinters. The statistical analysis of data collected on forty (N=40) subjects. For each of the chosen variable, the results pertaining to significant difference, if any, between experimental and control groups were assessed by "t" test and are presented in following tables:

Table 2. Muscular Power of Experimental Group Paired Samples t-Test

	Pre test	Post test
Sample size	20	20
Arithmetic mean	2.6120	2.6725
95% CI for the mean	2.5518 to 2.6722	2.6113 to 2.7337
Variance	0.01652	0.01713
Standard deviation	0.1285	0.1309
Standard error of the mean	0.02874	0.02926

Paired samples t-test

Mean difference	0.0605
Standard deviation	0.05586
95% CI	0.03435 to 0.08665
Test statistic t	4.843
Degrees of Freedom (DF)	19
Two-tailed probability	P = 0.0001

Table 3. Muscular Power of Control Group Paired Samples t-Test

	Pre Test	Post test
Sample size	20	20
Arithmetic mean	2.5880	2.5910
95% CI for the mean	2.5330 to 2.6430	2.5412 to 2.6408
Variance	0.0138	0.01133
Standard deviation	0.1175	0.1064
Standard error of the mean	0.02626	0.0238

Paired samples t-test

Mean difference	0.0030
Standard deviation	0.01525
95% CI	-0.004138 to 0.01014
Test statistic t	0.880
Degrees of Freedom (DF)	19
Two-tailed probability	P = 0.3900

TABLE-4
MEAN, STANDARD DEVIATION (SD), STANDARD ERROR OF MEAN (SEM) OF MUSCULAR
POWER OF EXPERIMENTAL AND CONTROL GROUP

Group	Number	Mean	S.D.	SEM	't' Value
Experiment (Pre-test)	20	2.612	0.128	0.028	4.843
Experimental (Post-test)	20	2.672	0.130	0.029	
Control (Pre-test)	20	2.588	0.117	0.026	0.880
Control (Post-test)	20	2.591	0.106	0.023	

*Significant at 0.05 level of confidence.

"t" .05 (19) = 2.093 Table-4 shows that the mean of Muscular power of pretest of experimental group and posttest of experimental group was 2.612 and 2.672 respectively, whereas the mean of muscular power of pre test of control and post test of control group was 2.588 and 2.591. The "t" value in case of experimental group was 4.843 and for control group it was 0.880. Since cal. t (=4.843) > tab t .05 (19) (=2.093), Ho (null hypothesis) is rejected at .05 level of significance. Thus it may be concluded that twelve week plyometric training programme showed significant improvement in muscular power. As per the study the above remark can be given at 95% confidence. The graphical representation of responses has been exhibited in figure-1.

Table 5. Anaerobic ability of Control Group Paired Samples t-Test

	Pre Test	Post Test
Sample size	20	20
Arithmetic mean	6.3800	6.3100
95% CI for the mean	6.2907 to 6.4693	6.2270 to 6.3930
Variance	0.03642	0.03147
Standard deviation	0.1908	0.1774
Standard error of the mean	0.04267	0.03967
Paired samples t-test		
Mean difference		-0.0700
Standard deviation		0.1081
95% CI		-0.1206 to -0.01941
Test statistic t		-2.896

Degrees of Freedom (DF)	19
Two-tailed probability	P = 0.0093

Table 6. Anaerobic ability of Control Group Paired Samples t-Test

	Pre Test	Post Test
Sample size	20	20
Arithmetic mean	6.5200	6.5250
95% CI for the mean	6.4563 to 6.5837	6.4608 to 6.5892
Variance	0.01853	0.01882
Standard deviation	0.1361	0.1372
Standard error of the mean	0.03044	0.03067
Paired samples t-test		
Mean difference		0.0050
Standard deviation		0.09987
95% CI		-0.04174 to 0.05174
Test statistic t		0.224
Degrees of Freedom (DF)		19
Two-tailed probability		P = 0.8252

**TABLE-7
MEAN, STANDARD DEVIATION (SD), STANDARD ERROR OF MEAN (SEM) OF ANAEROBIC ABILITY OF EXPERIMENTAL AND CONTROL GROUP**

Group	Number	Mean	S.D.	SEM	't' Value
Experiment (Pre-test)	20	6.380	0.190	0.042	2.896
Experimental (Post-test)	20	6.310	0.177	0.039	
Control (Pre-test)	20	6.520	0.136	0.03	0.224
Control (Post-test)	20	6.525	0.137	0.03	

***Significant at 0.05 level of confidence.**

"t" .05 (19) = **2.093**

Table-7 shows that the mean of anaerobic ability of pretest of experimental group and posttest of experimental group was 6.380 and 6.310 respectively, whereas the mean of anaerobic ability of pre test of control and post test of control group was 6.520 and 6.525. The "t" value in case of experimental group was 2.896 and for control group it was 0.224. Since cal. t (=2.896) > tab t .05 (19) (=2.093), Ho (null hypothesis) is rejected at .05 level of significance. Thus it may be concluded that twelve week plyometric training programme showed significant improvement in anaerobic ability. As per the study the above remark can be given at 95% confidence. The graphical representation of responses has been exhibited in figure-2.

DISCUSSION

Today the sports persons are trained scientifically with the latest training methods and sophisticated instruments for higher performance improvement in different sphere of sports. [1]. In this study, the 12-week of plyometric training programme showed significant improvement in muscular power and anaerobic ability. These findings are supported by other reports. Plyometric exercises increase muscular power and are most effective when designed to complement the specific movements required of the athletic activity [2]. Plyometric training technique is also the best for improving vertical jumping ability, positive energy production and elastic energy utilization [3]. 8-week sprint-specific plyometrics training program improve sprint performance. [4].

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the present study suggests that a Twelve week of plyometric training had significant effect on muscular power and anaerobic ability of noviced sprinters. The world of training methodology has crossed many milestones. In modern time athletes are being trained by highly sophisticated means for better achievements in their concerned sports, and greater stress has been laid on the quality rather than the quantity of training. Such training recommends to enhance similar training programmes on other games and sports where speed and explosiveness are important factors.

APPLICATIONS IN SPORT

The world of training methodology has crossed many milestones. In modern time athletes are being trained by highly sophisticated means for better achievements in their concerned sports, and greater stress has been laid on the quality rather than the quantity of training. Twelve weeks of Plyometric training exercises are useful program to improve the muscular power and anaerobic ability of noviced sprinters.

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